

Climate Change Rating of Countries 2022

Joseph Nowarski, M.Sc., ME – Energy Conservation Expert

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Abstract

This work applies a system of Climate Change Rating of countries (CCR). The parameters included in the rating are CO₂ emissions per capita and per GDP, cumulative CO₂ emissions in the last 30 years, and change of emissions in the last 10 years.

The parameters are compared to the world averages conservatively determined for every year.

The CCR for 2022 includes 209 countries, 99.999% of the global CO₂ emissions, 99.91 of the population, and 99.78% of the global GDP.

The A-G labels for rating groups are according to the CCR limits. The best rating (A) is for the lowest CCR. The average 2022 rating of Group A is 45 (56% below the world average) and of Group G – 206 (105% above the world average).

The world average CCR value for 2022 is 101.0, equivalent to Group F.

In 2022, Group A, the best group (Green Group), became larger. The number of A countries increased from 7 to 15. Group G, the worst group (Black Group), decreased by one country, and most importantly, the CO₂ emissions of this group decreased by 1%.

Three countries in Group G (Black Group) with the highest CO₂ emissions in 2022 - China, the US and Russia are responsible for 50% of the world's CO₂ emissions.

The position of all these countries on the CCR list worsened in 2022: China fell 3 places, the US 6 places (below China), and Russia 2 places.

China improved its CCR in 2022 from 158 to 157 and Russia from 175 to 170. The US CCR worsened in 2022 by 3 points from 155 to 158.

The US increased its CO2 emissions in 2022 by 1.0% while China and Russia reduced them by 0.7% and 5.9% respectively.

The publication and the linked website include the rating and the details of each country.

Glossary

Σ GDP	cumulative GDP in last 30 years, \$GDP
Ave	average
CCO ₂	global cumulative CO ₂ emissions according to publication [1] [2], CO ₂ emissions produced from fossil fuels and cement production only – land use change is not included, tCO ₂
CCp\$\$\$	country's cumulative CO ₂ emissions in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period
CCp\$\$\$W	weight of parameter CCp\$\$\$
CCR	Climate Change Rating of countries according to this work
CGP	Conservative Global Parameter, decreasing only world parameter applied to the CCR
CO ₂	emissions of Carbon Dioxide, CO ₂
Cp\$	country's CO ₂ emissions per GDP in the last year, tCO ₂ /\$GDP (ton CO ₂ per year, per \$GDP 2017 per year)
Cp\$10	country's change in Cp\$ in last 10 years, tCO ₂ /\$GDP
Cp\$10W	weight of parameter Cp\$10
Cp\$W	weight of parameter Cp\$
CpC	country's CO ₂ emissions per capita in the last year, tCO ₂ /y,cap
CpC10	country's change in CpC in last 10 years, tCO ₂ /y,cap
CpC10W	weight of parameter CpC10
CpCW	weight of parameter CpC
GDP	Gross Domestic Product, constant international \$ 2017, \$GDP/y
Global Warming	global surface temperature change over land+ocean above 1850-1900 baseline, °C
ktCO ₂ /y	kilo-ton CO ₂ = 1,000 metric tons of CO ₂ per year
MtCO ₂ /y	Mega-ton CO ₂ = 1,000,000 metric tons of CO ₂

OWID	Our World in Data – Internet site [2] [3]
tCO ₂	metric ton of CO ₂
tCO ₂ /y,cap	metric ton of CO ₂ per year, per capita
WB	World Bank
WCCp\$\$	CGP world cumulative CO ₂ emissions in last 30 years per cumulative GDP, tCO ₂ /\$GDP
WCp\$	CGP world CO ₂ emissions per GDP in the last year, tCO ₂ /\$GDP
WCp\$10	CGP world change in Cp\$ in last 10 years, tCO ₂ /\$GDP
WCpC	CGP world CO ₂ emissions per capita in the last year, tCO ₂ /y,cap
WCpC10	CGP world change in CpC in last 10 years, tCO ₂ /y,cap

Climate Change Rating of Countries

Nowagreen Climate Change Rating of Countries is described in the publication [1]. Publication [1] is related to the year 2020. The current publication is related to the Climate Change Rating of Countries in 2022.

Parameters Included in the Rating

Table 1 - Parameters included in the rating

Parameter	Country Symbol	World Symbol	Unit
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	WCp\$	tCO2/\$GDP
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	WCCp\$\$	tCO2/\$GDP
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CPC10	WCPC10	tCO2/y,cap
Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years	CP\$10	WCP\$10	tCO2/\$GDP

Weights of the CCR Parameters

Table 2 - CCR parameters weight

Parameter	Parameter Symbol	Weight	Weight Symbol
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	25%	CpCW
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	25%	Cp\$W
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	20%	CCp\$\$W
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	15%	CpC10W
Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years	Cp\$10	15%	Cp\$10W
Σ	5	100%	

A higher value of the calculations' result means worse CCR (more CO2 emissions).

Sources of Data

The datasets are from the following sources:

- OWID [2] [3] CO2 emissions produced from fossil fuels and cement production only – land use change is not included
- World Bank (WB) [4] GDP, PPP (constant 2021 international \$)

CO2 emissions are without international transport.

Table 3 - Dataset [2] [3] [4]

	CO2 emissions	GDP	Population
Source of data	OWID	World Bank/OWID/UN	OWID
Reference	[3]	[4]	[2]
Countries	209	209	209
From year	1990	1990	1990
To year	2022	2022	2022
CO2 from fossil fuels	Yes		
CO2 from cement production	Yes		
CO2 from other sources	No		
Other GHG	No		
Land use change	No		
International transport	No		
Units	tCO2/y	Constant International \$ 2021	
Resolution	1 tCO2/y	1	1

Table 4 - Completeness of data

		Dataset	World	Dataset to World
countries		209	240	87.08%
CO2 emissions	MtCO2/y	36,100	36,100	100.00%
Population	Ex6	7,968	7,975	99.91%
GDP	Ex9\$	138,675	138,977	99.78%

Conversion of GDP Data

The GDP units as in WB publication [4] are “constant 2021 international \$”.

However, the CCR for previous years is based on “2017 International \$”.

CCR 2022 applies data from CCR 2021 till the year 2021 and GDP for 2022 was converted from [4] “2021 international \$” to “2017 international \$” using data for USA.

World Data for the Year 2022

Table 5 - World data for the year 2022

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	World 2022
CO2 emissions in 2022		tCO2/y	36,100,459,000
Cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years		tCCO2	890,973,811,800
CO2 emissions before 10 years		tCO2/y	33,838,743,000
Population			7,975,105,024
Population before 10 years			7,161,697,792
GDP		\$GDP/y	138,976,832,954,482
Cumulative GDP in the last 30 years		\$\$GDP	2,758,701,368,546,070
GDP before 10 years		\$GDP/y	104,018,222,159,394
CpC before 10 years		tCO2/y,cap	4.72
Cp\$ before 10 years		tCO2/\$GDP	0.000325
CO2 emissions per capita	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap	4.53
CO2 emissions per GDP	WCp\$	tCO2/\$GDP	0.000260
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	WCCp\$\$	tCCO2/\$\$GDP	0.000323
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	CpC10	tCO2/y,cap	96%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	Cp\$10	tCO2/\$GDP	80%

Table 6 - World data for the year 2022 compared to 2021

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	2022	2021	Δ
CO2 emissions per capita	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap	4.53	4.56	-0.73%
CO2 emissions per GDP	WCp\$	tCO2/\$GDP	0.000260	0.000268	-3.08%
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	WCCp\$\$	tCCO2/\$\$GDP	0.000323	0.000328	-1.53%
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	CpC10	tCO2/y,cap	96%	97%	-1.23%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	Cp\$10	tCO2/\$GDP	80%	81%	-1.42%

All CCR world parameters were improved in 2022 comparing to 2021. The biggest improvement was in CO2 emissions per GDP (Cp\$) – 3.08%.

Conservative Global Parameters

The CCR world parameters change every year. There will be years when some world parameters will increase and some will decrease.

To ensure a conservative approach to the CCR, the "Conservative Global Parameters" (CGP) is applied every year instead of the actual world averages of this year. If the value of the world parameter decreases below the value of the previous year Conservative Global Parameter (CGP), the new Conservative Global Parameter (CGP) will change to the actual value of the world parameter. If the value of the world parameter is above the last CGP, the CGP for the current year will remain the same as in the previous year.

Table 7 - Conservative Global Parameters for 2022

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	World 2022	CGP2021	CGP2022
CO2 emissions per capita	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap	4.52664	4.37774	4.37774
CO2 emissions per GDP	WCp\$	tCO2/\$GDP	0.000259759	0.000268347	0.000259759
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	WCCp\$\$	tCO2/\$\$GDP	0.000322969	0.000328360	0.000322969
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	CpC10	tCO2/y,cap	95.8028%	94.7267%	94.7267%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	Cp\$10	tCO2/\$GDP	79.8483%	81.0608%	79.8483%

Table 8 - CCR Index for the World in 2022

Parameter	Parameter	Value	Weight	Index
	Symbol			
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	103%	25%	26%
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	100%	25%	25%
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	100%	20%	20%
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	101%	15%	15%
Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years	Cp\$10	100%	15%	15%
Σ			100%	101%

The CCR Index for the world in the year 2022 is 101.

Example for Israel

Table 9 - Basic parameters for CCR for Israel

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Israel	CGP2022	Israel to CGP2022
CO2 emissions in 2022	CO2	tCO2/y	56,118,000		
Population			9,038,313		
GDP	GDP	\$GDP/y	424,288,967,593		
Cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years	CCO2	tCCO2	1,777,936,500		
Cumulative GDP in the last 30 years	ΣGDP	\$GDP	7,557,462,310,251		
CpC before 10 years		tCO2/y,cap	9.8504		
Cp\$ before 10 years		tCO2/\$GDP	0.0002637		
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	tCO2/y,cap	6.2089	4.3777	142%
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	tCO2/\$GDP	0.0001323	0.0002683	49%
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	tCCO2/\$GDP	0.0002353	0.0003284	72%
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	CpC10	tCO2/y,cap	63.03%	94.73%	67%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	Cp\$10	tCO2/\$GDP	50.16%	81.06%	62%

Table 10 - CCR Index for Israel in 2022

Parameter	Parameter Symbol	Value	Weight	Index
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	142%	25%	35%
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	49%	25%	12%
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	72%	20%	14%
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	67%	15%	10%
Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years	Cp\$10	62%	15%	9%
Σ			100%	81%

The CCR Index for Israel in the year 2022 is 81 (much better than the world average)

CCR details for each country are available on the website [6].

Table 11 - Israel's CCR country page [6]

Nowagreen Climate Change Rating of Countries - CCR 2022	
country: Israel (ISR) 2022	
country	Israel
country code	ISR
CCR year	2022
CO2 emissions per capita (CpC), tCO2/y,cap	6.21
CpC to World	142%
CpC weight	35%
CO2 emissions per GDP (Cp\$), tCO2/\$GDP	0.000132
Cp\$ to World	51%
Cp\$ weight	10%
cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP (CCp\$\$), tCO2/\$GDP	0.000235
CCp\$\$ to World	73%
CCp\$\$ weight	15%
change in CO2 emissions per capita in the last 10 years (CpC10), tCO2/y,cap	63%
CpC10 to World	67%
CpC10 weight	10%
change in CO2 emissions per GDP in the last 10 years (Cp\$10), tCO2/\$GDP	50%
Cp\$10 to World	67%
Cp\$10 weight	9%
CCR Rating a lower number means less CO2 and a better rating	82
country position on the CCR list of a total 209	104
A-G CCR label	D

Countries with CCR Below and Above the World Average

The world CCR in 2022 is 101.0207 (compared to 101.4 in 2021).

Table 12 - Countries with CCR below and above the world average in 2022

	Countries	%	tCO2/y	%
CCR<101	144	69%	10,179,401,689	28%
CCR>101	65	31%	25,920,810,342	72%
Σ	209		36,100,212,031	

69% of the countries have a better CCR rating than the world average in 2022. However, the 31% minority of the countries with CCR worse than the world average is responsible for 72% of the world's CO2 emissions (73% in 2021).

Rating A-G

Rating A-G includes 7 groups.

Table 13 - A-G groups

Rating	min CCR	max CCR	Color
A		50	Light Green
B	51	60	Dark Green
C	61	70	Light Blue
D	71	85	Dark Blue
E	86	100	Violet
F	101	150	Red
G	151		Black

Table 14 - A-G CCR groups in 2022

Rating	countries	Ave CCR	tCO ₂ /y	%
A	15	45	86,277,045	0%
B	21	56	390,530,576	1%
C	26	66	1,343,777,066	4%
D	51	77	2,096,959,858	6%
E	31	92	6,261,857,144	17%
F	37	121	3,981,985,508	11%
G	28	206	21,938,824,834	61%
Σ	209		36,100,212,031	100%

Table 15 - A-D E-G CCR groups in 2022

Rating	countries	Ave CCR	tCO ₂ /y	%
A-D	113	62	3,917,544,545	11%
E-G	96	140	32,182,667,486	89%

Table 16 - Group A

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
A	15	45	List #	86,277,045
LKA	Sri Lanka	49	13	17,327,070
AGO	Angola	36	2	16,070,300
CIV	Cote d'Ivoire	46	5	11,734,200
YEM	Yemen	48	9	11,356,360
CMR	Cameroon	48	8	9,572,640
UGA	Uganda	48	10	6,021,786
COD	Democratic Republic of Congo	39	3	3,601,600
NER	Niger	50	14	3,058,156
HTI	Haiti	47	6	2,446,680
MLT	Malta	49	11	1,655,130
SLE	Sierra Leone	50	15	1,129,488
LBR	Liberia	47	7	876,934
SOM	Somalia	30	1	646,920
DJI	Djibouti	41	4	453,036
GNB	Guinea-Bissau	49	12	326,745

Table 17 - Group B

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
B	21	56	List #	390,530,576
NGA	Nigeria	55	22	128,759,600
BGD	Bangladesh	59	33	102,103,400
SWE	Sweden	58	30	38,050,600
CHE	Switzerland	59	34	35,380,300
GHA	Ghana	57	25	20,806,930
ETH	Ethiopia	60	35	19,073,260
TZA	Tanzania	54	21	15,570,020
URY	Uruguay	58	28	7,893,090
CRI	Costa Rica	52	17	7,888,690
MDG	Madagascar	58	29	4,403,590
TGO	Togo	52	16	2,575,570
MWI	Malawi	58	31	2,094,074
RWA	Rwanda	57	27	1,547,760
SWZ	Eswatini	59	32	1,265,050
FJI	Fiji	57	24	1,073,924
TLS	East Timor	53	20	668,892
CPV	Cape Verde	60	36	568,778
SLB	Solomon Islands	56	23	298,633
CAF	Central African Republic	52	18	226,226
LIE	Liechtenstein	52	19	149,934
STP	Sao Tome and Principe	57	26	132,255

Table 18 - Group C

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
C	26	66	List #	1,343,777,066
BRA	Brazil	68	51	483,478,000
GBR	United Kingdom	69	55	318,664,000
PAK	Pakistan	65	46	200,200,000
COL	Colombia	66	48	99,717,900
HKG	Hong Kong	61	37	30,568,900
DNK	Denmark	69	57	29,059,400
KEN	Kenya	68	52	24,851,930
DOM	Dominican Republic	62	41	23,637,950
SDN	Sudan	64	43	22,013,370
GTM	Guatemala	70	58	19,193,250
AFG	Afghanistan	70	59	12,147,960
PAN	Panama	61	40	11,899,900
HND	Honduras	69	56	11,159,710
PRY	Paraguay	70	62	9,018,060
SLV	El Salvador	64	44	7,714,380
LVA	Latvia	70	60	6,591,400
GAB	Gabon	70	61	5,705,520
NIC	Nicaragua	62	42	5,550,360
ALB	Albania	61	39	4,954,750
GIN	Guinea	69	54	4,953,610
NAM	Namibia	69	53	3,952,970
PSE	Palestine Authority	67	50	3,496,896
TCD	Chad	66	49	2,369,204
BTN	Bhutan	66	47	1,055,528
MAC	Macao	61	38	1,051,646
GMB	Gambia	65	45	770,472

Table 19 - Group D

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
D	51	77	List #	2,096,959,858
ITA	Italy	85	111	338,098,000
FRA	France	71	67	297,532,000
EGY	Egypt	75	84	258,951,700
ESP	Spain	81	103	245,613,000
PHL	Philippines	75	80	150,395,900
CHL	Chile	84	109	84,377,700
VEN	Venezuela	75	83	76,891,500
ROU	Romania	72	72	73,521,000
MAR	Morocco	81	100	68,411,900
PER	Peru	71	63	60,921,100
ISR	Israel	82	104	56,118,000
HUN	Hungary	80	96	44,353,600
ECU	Ecuador	80	97	41,613,300
PRT	Portugal	72	71	41,605,000
IRL	Ireland	83	107	38,784,000
JOR	Jordan	75	81	22,912,560
BOL	Bolivia	78	93	21,493,740
CUB	Cuba	73	77	20,921,000
HRV	Croatia	79	95	17,526,000
LTU	Lithuania	77	90	12,667,300
SEN	Senegal	71	69	11,668,420
GEO	Georgia	84	110	11,092,940
KGZ	Kyrgyzstan	78	94	9,449,740
ZMB	Zambia	76	86	8,921,890
ZWE	Zimbabwe	74	79	8,856,000
BEN	Benin	75	82	8,432,160
PNG	Papua New Guinea	76	85	7,823,140
BWA	Botswana	83	108	7,467,290
JAM	Jamaica	83	106	6,487,600
ARM	Armenia	71	65	6,407,780
BFA	Burkina Faso	73	76	5,962,166
MDA	Moldova	76	87	5,422,000
GNQ	Equatorial Guinea	81	101	5,076,210
MRT	Mauritania	76	88	4,534,100
MUS	Mauritius	77	89	4,249,020
MNE	Montenegro	81	102	2,292,500
BHS	Bahamas	85	113	2,120,000
SSD	South Sudan	77	91	1,833,602
MDV	Maldives	78	92	1,701,072
PYF	French Polynesia	71	70	873,218
BDI	Burundi	72	73	798,451
BLZ	Belize	85	112	725,230
LCA	Saint Lucia	74	78	470,351
AND	Andorra	72	74	368,645
GRD	Grenada	80	99	340,416
WSM	Samoa	82	105	249,491
VCT	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	71	68	238,739
VGB	British Virgin Islands	71	66	156,784
DMA	Dominica	72	75	153,220
KIR	Kiribati	80	98	68,043
TUV	Tuvalu	71	64	11,340

Table 20 - Group E

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
E	31	92	List #	6,261,857,144
IND	India	94	134	2,829,643,000
IDN	Indonesia	87	116	728,885,000
DEU	Germany	100	144	665,600,000
MEX	Mexico	87	120	511,972,000
TUR	Turkey	87	118	435,686,000
THA	Thailand	89	125	270,746,200
ARG	Argentina	87	119	192,864,000
NLD	Netherlands	89	124	125,358,000
BEL	Belgium	99	142	89,605,000
AUT	Austria	90	127	61,488,000
GRC	Greece	90	126	59,662,700
SGP	Singapore	98	139	53,252,600
NOR	Norway	91	129	40,807,900
FIN	Finland	88	123	36,163,000
TUN	Tunisia	98	140	35,576,770
NZL	New Zealand	86	115	32,211,900
SYR	Syria	100	143	27,635,200
NPL	Nepal	95	135	15,499,950
SVN	Slovenia	88	122	12,714,830
MOZ	Mozambique	94	133	8,003,210
MKD	North Macedonia	91	130	7,588,410
MLI	Mali	90	128	7,038,754
CYP	Cyprus	94	132	7,029,340
GUY	Guyana	88	121	3,537,120
BRB	Barbados	99	141	1,232,830
ERI	Eritrea	93	131	696,824
BMU	Bermuda	96	137	445,408
COM	Comoros	97	138	412,760
KNA	Saint Kitts and Nevis	86	114	224,486
VUT	Vanuatu	87	117	207,909
COK	Cook Islands	95	136	68,043

Table 21 - Group F

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO ₂ /y
F	37	121	List #	3,981,985,508
JPN	Japan	111	156	1,053,798,000
KOR	South Korea	141	179	601,000,000
VNM	Vietnam	125	166	343,606,300
POL	Poland	121	164	323,117,000
MYS	Malaysia	135	176	291,071,000
TWN	Taiwan	137	178	277,901,000
IRQ	Iraq	125	167	179,080,700
DZA	Algeria	114	158	176,345,000
UKR	Ukraine	115	159	141,252,000
UZB	Uzbekistan	136	177	120,610,000
CZE	Czechia	124	165	97,969,000
BLR	Belarus	129	172	58,801,000
BGR	Bulgaria	120	163	46,147,500
SRB	Serbia	126	168	43,506,400
AZE	Azerbaijan	104	146	38,062,600
MMR	Myanmar	109	149	34,922,200
SVK	Slovakia	101	145	34,151,700
LBN	Lebanon	116	160	23,904,560
KHM	Cambodia	132	175	19,955,040
BIH	Bosnia and Herzegovina	127	170	19,735,750
EST	Estonia	111	155	10,311,800
TJK	Tajikistan	119	161	10,017,370
XKX	Kosovo	126	169	8,017,524
LUX	Luxembourg	107	148	7,524,090
COG	Congo	110	150	7,431,920
SUR	Suriname	146	181	3,586,520
ISL	Iceland	111	154	3,542,510
LSO	Lesotho	129	171	3,134,696
ABW	Aruba	110	152	865,876
SYC	Seychelles	110	151	658,828
ATG	Antigua and Barbuda	120	162	602,192
GRL	Greenland	131	173	591,716
TCA	Turks and Caicos Islands	131	174	349,200
TON	Tonga	110	153	189,008
FSM	Micronesia (country)	113	157	151,206
NRU	Nauru	146	180	52,922
MSR	Montserrat	105	147	21,380

Table 22 - Group G

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO ₂ /y
G	28	206	List#	21,938,824,834
CHN	China	157	185	11,396,780,000
USA	United States	158	186	5,057,290,000
RUS	Russia	170	192	1,652,178,000
IRN	Iran	159	188	690,635,000
SAU	Saudi Arabia	196	196	662,550,000
CAN	Canada	161	189	547,945,000
ZAF	South Africa	155	182	404,051,000
AUS	Australia	166	191	392,280,000
KAZ	Kazakhstan	208	197	271,179,000
ARE	United Arab Emirates	235	200	243,895,400
KWT	Kuwait	260	206	109,190,100
QAT	Qatar	310	208	101,340,500
OMN	Oman	188	195	71,986,500
TKM	Turkmenistan	230	198	70,958,700
LBY	Libya	164	190	62,961,100
PRK	North Korea	240	205	50,871,800
MNG	Mongolia	238	203	37,894,550
BHR	Bahrain	264	207	37,795,600
TTO	Trinidad and Tobago	317	209	34,331,800
LAO	Laos	237	202	23,193,410
BRN	Brunei	232	199	10,753,700
NCL	New Caledonia	236	201	5,115,210
CUW	Curacao	186	194	1,756,650
FRO	Faroe Islands	156	184	748,134
SXM	Sint Maarten (Dutch part)	179	193	634,258
PLW	Palau	240	204	219,249
MHL	Marshall Islands	156	183	151,206
AIA	Anguilla	158	187	138,967

World CCR Rating

In 2022 the world CCR was improved from 101.4 in 2021 to 101.0, which is still the same group, Group F, the Red group.

The main reason for the change is the world's CO₂ emissions per GDP, which was reduced in 2022 by 3.2%.

Changes from CCR 2021

Table 23 - Changes in CCR 2021-2022

Rating	countries 2021	countries 2022	change	Ave CCR 2021	Ave CCR 2022	change	MtCO ₂ /y 2021	MtCO ₂ /y 2022	change
A	7	15	+8	38	45	19%	35	86	149%
B	31	21	-10	55	56	3%	470	391	-17%
C	22	26	+4	66	66	1%	310	1,344	334%
D	51	51	+0	78	77	-1%	4,133	2,097	-49%
E	33	31	-2	93	92	-1%	4,274	6,262	47%
F	35	37	+2	117	121	3%	4,691	3,982	-15%
G	29	28	-1	212	206	-3%	22,179	21,939	-1%
Σ	208	209	+1				36,092	36,100	0.02%

In 2022, Group A, the best group (the green group), became larger. The number of A countries increased from 7 to 15. Group G, the worst group (the black group), decreased by one country, and most importantly, the CO₂ emissions of this group decreased by 1%.

Table 24 - 3 countries in Group G (Black Group) with the highest CO₂ emissions in 2022

Rating		CCR 2021	CCR 2022	CCR List # 2021	CCR List # 2022	MtCO ₂ /y 18,235 2021	MtCO ₂ /y 18,106 2022	Δ
G								
CHN	China	158	157	182	185	11,472	11,397	-0.7%
USA	United States	155	158	180	186	5,007	5,057	+1.0%
RUS	Russia	175	170	190	192	1,756	1,652	-5.9%

Three countries in Group G (Black Group) with the highest CO₂ emissions in 2022 - China, the US and Russia are responsible for 50% of the world's CO₂ emissions. The position of all these countries on the CCR list worsened in 2022: China fell 3 places, the US 6 places (below China), and Russia 2 places.

China improved its CCR in 2022 from 158 to 157 and Russia from 175 to 170. The US CCR worsened in 2022 by 3 points from 155 to 158.

The US increased its CO₂ emissions in 2022 by 1.0% while China and Russia reduced them by 0.7% and 5.9% respectively.

Climate Change Rating of Countries on the Website

The Climate Change Rating of countries according to this work for the years 2020, 2021 and 2022 is available on the website [5].

Details of a specific country can be retrieved on site [6].

Table 25 - Climate Change Rating of Countries 2022 on the Website [5]

Nowgreen Climate Change Rating of Countries - CCR 2022 sorted by country code				
for more details click on country code				
country code	country	CCR	position on CCR list	A-G Rating
ABW	Aruba	110	152	F
AFG	Afghanistan	70	59	C
AGO	Angola	36	2	A
AIA	Anguilla	158	187	G
ALB	Albania	61	39	C
AND	Andorra	72	74	D
ARE	United Arab Emirates	235	200	G
ARG	Argentina	87	119	E
ARM	Armenia	71	65	D
ATG	Antigua and Barbuda	120	162	F
AUS	Australia	166	191	G
AUT	Austria	90	127	E
AZE	Azerbaijan	104	146	F
BDI	Burundi	72	73	D
BEL	Belgium	99	142	E
BEN	Benin	75	82	D
country code	country	CCR	position on CCR list	A-G Rating
BFA	Burkina Faso	73	76	D
BGD	Bangladesh	59	33	B
BGR	Bulgaria	120	163	F

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